

PHYSICOCHEMICAL STUDY OF THE As_2Te_3 - TlGaSe_2 SYSTEM AND X-RAY AND ELECTROPHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF SOLID SOLUTION ALLOYS

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Abstract

The As_2Te_3 - TlGaSe_2 system was studied using physicochemical analytical methods (DTA, MSA, X-ray diffraction, as well as microhardness and density determination), and its T-x phase diagram was constructed. The phase diagram of the As_2Te_3 - TlGaSe_2 system was found to be quasi-binary and eutectic. The composition of the eutectic formed in the system is 20 mol. % TlGaSe_2 , and the temperature is 275°C. Microstructural analysis showed that at room temperature, solid solutions based on As_2Te_3 reach up to 3 mol. % TlGaSe_2 , while those based on the TlGaSe_2 compound reach 7 mol. % As_2Te_3 . The temperature dependence of the electrical conductivity and thermoelectric power of the $(\text{As}_2\text{Te}_3)_{1-x}(\text{TlGaSe}_2)_x$ ($x = 0.01; 0.03$) solid solution alloys was studied.

Keywords: phase, eutectic, quasi-binarity, microhardness, solid solution.

Introduction

Arsenic chalcogenides of main subgroup V are classic glassy semiconductors with functional properties. Sulfide and selenide arsenic compounds are glassy under ambient conditions, while telluride compounds are crystalline. Arsenic chalcogenides, as well as ternary and more complex phases obtained from them, are materials with photovoltaic [1–4] and luminescent [5, 6] properties. Semiconductor fibers obtained from glassy arsenic compounds are currently being widely studied [7–10].

The compound As_2Te_2 and new phases and solid solutions obtained from it are materials with low-resistance photovoltaic properties [11–13]. A number of systems consisting of arsenic chalcogenides have been studied in the literature [14–18].

The aim of this work is to construct the T-x phase diagram of the As_2Te_3 - TlGaSe_2 system by means of its physicochemical study and to investigate the electrophysical properties of the obtained phases.

The components of the As_2Te_3 - TlGaSe_2 system have the following crystal structure.

The As_2Te_3 compound melts congruently at 381°C and crystallizes in the monoclinic syngony, the lattice parameters are: $a = 14.339 \text{ \AA}$; $b = 4.006 \text{ \AA}$; $c = 9.873 \text{ \AA}$, $\beta = 95^\circ$, sp. gr. $C2/m$ [19]. The TlGaSe_2 compound melts at 817°C and crystallizes in the tetragonal syngony, the lattice parameters are: $a = 7.62 \text{ \AA}$; $c = 30.50 \text{ \AA}$, $Z = 16$, $\rho = 6.47 \text{ g/cm}^3$, density $\rho = 6.44 \text{ g/cm}^3$ [20]. The authors [21] show that the TlGaSe_2 compound crystallizes in the monoclinic syngony with the lattice parameters: $a = 10.772 \text{ \AA}$; $b = 10.771 \text{ \AA}$; $c = 15.635 \text{ \AA}$. $\beta = 100.6^\circ$; $z = 16$.

Experimental Section

Alloys of the As_2Te_3 - TlGaSe_2 system were synthesized using the ampoule method by co-melting pre-synthesized As_2Te_3 and TlGaSe_2 starting materials in a quartz ampoule evacuated to a pressure of 0.133 MPa. To achieve equilibrium, the alloys were heat-treated at 275°C for 300 hours.

The equilibrium state of the alloys was studied using physicochemical analysis (DTA, X-ray diffraction, and microarray analysis), as well as microhardness and density measurements.

DTA analysis of the alloys was performed on a THERMOSCAN-2 pyrometer using a chromel-alumel thermocouple at a heating rate of 5°C/min. X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis was performed on a D2 PHASER X-ray diffractometer. Microstructural analysis was performed on an MIM-8 metallographic microscope. Microhardness was measured using a PMT-3 instrument. The density of the alloys in the system was determined by pycnometric weighing, using toluene as the working fluid. Physical measurements were carried out using the compensation method [22].

Results and Discussion

The synthesized As_2Te_3 - TlGaSe_2 alloys are dense gray masses. They are highly soluble in hot acids (HNO_3 and H_2SO_4) and alkalis (NaOH , KOH). After reaching equilibrium, the As_2Te_3 - TlGaSe_2 alloys were studied using physicochemical analysis. Thermal analysis of the alloys revealed two endothermic effects in the thermograms of the samples: one related to the solidus and the other related to the solidus.

Microstructural analysis of the alloys revealed the presence of single-phase regions in a limited region surrounding the starting components. The remaining alloys are biphasic. Figure 1 shows the microstructure of alloys containing 3, 50, and 93 mol. % TlGaSe_2 .

Fig. 1. Microstructure of As_2Te_3 - $TlGaSe_2$ alloys.
a) - 3 mol. %, b) - 50 mol. %, c) - 93 mol. % $TlGaSe_2$

Single-phase alloys containing 3 mol.% and 93 mol.% $TlGaSe_2$ are solid solutions based on As_2Te_3 and $TlGaSe_2$, respectively. The sample containing 50 mol.% $TlGaSe_2$ belongs to the two-phase region.

To confirm the results of differential thermal and microstructural analyses, X-ray diffraction analysis of samples from individual regions of the system was performed.

Fig. 2. Diffraction patterns of As_2Te_3 - $TlGaSe_2$ alloys.
1 - As_2Te_3 , 2 - 20 mol. %, 3 - 50 mol. %, 4 - 93 mol. %, 5 - 100 mol. % $TlGaSe_2$.

Diffraction patterns of As_2Te_3 - $TlGaSe_2$ alloys with concentrations of 20, 50, and 93 mol. % $TlGaSe_2$ are shown in Fig. 2. As can be seen from the figure, the diffraction lines present in the diffraction patterns of the alloys containing 20 and 50 mol. % $TlGaSe_2$ are a mixture of the diffraction lines of the original components. These samples are two-phase alloys. In the diffraction pattern of the 93 mol. % $TlGaSe_2$ sample, the serpentine diffraction lines are identical to those of the $TlGaSe_2$ compound. They differ slightly only in their interplanar spacings. This sample is a solid solution alloy based on the compound $TlGaSe_2$. Thus, the results of differential thermal and microstructural analysis were confirmed by X-ray diffraction analysis.

Based on the results of a comprehensive physico-chemical analysis, a T-x phase diagram was constructed for the As_2Te_3 - $TlGaSe_2$ system (Fig. 3). The diagram is quasi-binary and eutectic. The composition of the eutectic formed between the As_2Te_3 and $TlGaSe_2$ compounds is 20 mol. % $TlGaSe_2$, and the temperature is 275°C. At room temperature, solid solutions based on As_2Te_3 in the system reach up to 3 mol. % $TlGaSe_2$, while 7 mol. % As_2Te_3 dissolves in the $TlGaSe_2$ compound.

The liquidus line of the As_2Te_3 - $TlGaSe_2$ system consists of monovariant equilibrium curves for the α -solid solution based on the As_2Te_3 compound and the β -solid solution based on $TlGaSe_2$.

Fig. 3. T - x phase diagram of the As_2Te_3 - $TlGaSe_2$ system.

Primary crystals of the α -solid solution precipitate in the range of 0–20 mol% $TlGaSe_2$. Crystallization of the β -solid solution from the liquid occurs in the concentration range of 20–100 mol % $TlGaSe_2$. Below the

solidus line, in the range of 3–97 mol % $TlGaSe_2$, two-phase alloys consisting of ($\alpha + \beta$) crystallize. Table 1 lists some physicochemical properties of the As_2Te_3 - $TlGaSe_2$ system.

Table 1.

Composition of As_2Te_3 - $TlGaSe_2$ alloys, DTA results, density and microhardness measurement results

Composition, mol %		Thermal effects, °C	Density, q/cm^3	Microhardness, MPa	
As_2Te_3	$TlGaSe_2$			α	β
100	0,0	381	5,40	1600	–
97	3,0	315,375	5,42	1650	–
95	5,0	275,365	5,47	1670	–
90	10	275,350	5,50	1670	–
85	15	275,320	5,56	–	–
80	20	275	5,61	Eutec.	Eutec.
70	30	275,410	5,71	–	–
60	40	275,525	5,82	–	770
50	50	275,615	5,92	–	770
40	60	275,675	6,02	–	770
30	70	275,740	6,13	–	770
20	80	275,775	6,23	–	770
10	90	275,800	6,40	–	770
5.0	95	530,819	6,47	–	750
0.0	100	817	6,44	–	700

When measuring the microhardness of As_2Te_3 - $TlGaSe_2$ alloys, two different microhardness values were determined. The microhardness of α -solid solution alloys obtained from As_2Te_3 varied in the range of 1600–1670 MPa. The microhardness of β -solid solution alloys based on $TlGaSe_2$ was 700–770 MPa.

The temperature dependence of the electrical conductivity and thermal emf of $(As_2Te_3)_{1-x}(TlGaSe_2)_x$ ($x = 0.01; 0.03$) solid solution alloys was studied (Fig. 4). Samples of the specified compositions were cooled

equally slowly. Measurements were carried out in the temperature range of 300–600 K.

As can be seen from the temperature dependence graph of the electrical conductivity of samples with concentrations of 1 and 3 mol. % $TlGaSe_2$, it increases linearly with temperature and composition. Electrical conductivity is mediated by an electronic mechanism. In the range of 300–400 K, impurity conductivity appears. In the range of 400–600 K, intrinsic conductivity begins, increasing rapidly with temperature.

Fig. 4. Temperature dependence of the electrical conductivity of $(As_2Te_3)_{1-x}(TlGaSe_2)_x$ ($x = 0.01$; 0.03) solid solution alloys. 1-1 mol. %, 2-3 mol. % TlGaSe₂.

Fig. 5. Temperature dependence of the thermo-EMF of $(As_2Te_3)_{1-x}(TlGaSe_2)_x$ ($x = 0.01$; 0.03) solid solution alloys. 1-1 mol. %, 2-3 mol. % TlGaSe₂.

Figure 5 shows the temperature dependence of the thermoelectric power of $(As_2Te_3)_{1-x}(TlGaSe_2)_x$ solid solutions ($x = 0.01$; 0.03). The thermoelectric power increases with temperature, reaching a maximum at 400 K, and then begins to decrease. This dependence is in good agreement with the temperature dependence of electrical conductivity.

Conclusion

To study phase equilibrium in the As_2Te_3 -TlGaSe₂ system, samples were synthesized over a wide concentration range. The samples were then heat-treated at 270°C for 700 hours and allowed to reach equilibrium. The alloys were studied using physicochemical analysis (DTA, MSA, X-ray diffraction, and microhardness and density determinations), and a T-x phase diagram of the As_2Te_3 -TlGaSe₂ system was constructed. It was established that the As_2Te_3 -TlGaSe₂ system is quasi-binary and belongs to the eutectic type. The composition of the resulting eutectic is 20 mol. % TlGaSe₂, and the temperature is 275°C. At room temperature, the solubility of As_2Te_3 -based solid solutions in the system reaches up to 3 mol. % TlGaSe₂, while solid solutions based on the TlGaSe₂ compound extend up to 7 mol. % As_2Te_3 . The dependence of the electrical conductivity and thermoelectric power of the $(As_2Te_3)_{1-x}(TlGaSe_2)_x$ ($x=0.01$; 0.03) solid solution alloys on temperature and composition was studied. The alloys are semiconductors with medium resistance.

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